

Statistics of Goldbach Prime Pairs for Even Numbers

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Abstract

Earlier this year I wrote a paper with my brother (see "*Why the Goldbach conjecture is likely true*", Ismael Afaf and Mikhael Afaf, 18th Feb 2023), where we computed the exact number of Goldbach Prime Pairs (GPPs) for even numbers up to 80,000 and showed that the number of pairs increases on average as $\frac{N}{\ln N}$. I then wrote a second paper (see "*How the Prime Number Theorem likely implies not just the simple Goldbach Conjecture but a much stronger version*", Ismael Afaf, 22nd Jun 2023) about how I could deduce the probable number of Goldbach Prime Pairs per even number as a result of the Prime Number Theorem and showed it matched almost perfectly with the running average of the exact computed Goldbach Prime Pairs. In this paper I show that when I partition even number numbers, upto 367,800, into non-overlapping intervals of 100 points each, and then look at the Mean and Standard Deviation of exactly computed GPPs in each interval, I match almost exactly the probabilistic deduction from the PMT described in my 2nd paper - with Excel regression showing fits at an R^2 square value of 0.9998. I also see that the Mean is roughly 2.55 times the Standard Deviation of GPPs in each interval, staying in a very tight range between 2.5 and 2.7 with some small oscillations. I also plot the resulting graphs against $N/\ln(N)$ and the more precise approximation of $\text{Li}(x)$ I used in my previous paper, showing how both are a very good fit. Finally, I discuss why the number of GPPs oscillations show a standard deviation per interval that is almost directly proportional to the Mean GPP per interval.

Dedication: I would also like to dedicate this paper to my 11 year brother Mikki (Mikhael Afaf) who was co-author in the first paper. Mikki was actually responsible for kick starting the Goldbach Prime Pairs investigations back in Dec 2022 when he conjectured that the number of GPPs likely grew with each increasing number. Despite being visually impaired with XLRN for 6 years, never supported by schools, with no appropriately modified reading materials, screen sharing software, extra time for tests,

counselling, Mikki has to be home schooled but never complains. Despite not having a school to attend, always treated unfairly, he has so many ideas that I find it impossible to catch up with him. I attended the all day RetinaUK Annual conference with him in London on Saturday the 24th of June and this ended up delaying the writing of this paper, but all for a good cause.

Acknowledgement: I would also like to thank my dad, Nasir Afaf for proof-reading, suggesting Mean and Standard Deviation computations, major stylistic changes, plus encouraging me to start and finish this paper after I had obtained the statistical results.

1 Background

In my previous paper (see "*How the Prime Number Theorem likely implies not just the simple Goldbach Conjecture but a much stronger version*", Ismael Afaf, 22nd Jun 2023) I stated that I observed the oscillations in the number of Goldbach Prime Pairs as the even number increases and that I would look into this phenomenon later. After writing and submitting the paper on the evening of June 22nd 2023, as I went to bed I thought about the oscillations of the Goldbach prime pairs and how they do not increase evenly but jump up and down, with these ups and downs steadily increasing as the even number increases, optically almost in the same functional form that the average number of GPPs increased. I then decided maybe the best thing was to get some statistics on the exact computed numbers. I asked my father, Nasir Afaf, and he said maybe I could write a code to return Mean and Standard Deviation of the exact GPPs that I had computed. Just before going to bed I read some descriptions on the internet that explained Mean, Standard Deviation, Skew and Kurtosis. I decided I would compute these and compare to my previously obtained results.

2 Result

On the morning of 23rd June 2023, I decided that the fastest and best way was to use ChatGPT help to write Python code that would read the previously computed exact GPPs Time Series from my Excel file, divide them into N overlapping partitions where N is user input, and return an Excel file where the rows were partition number and the columns Mean, Variance, Skew and Kurtosis respectively.

The results thrilled me, which I share below:

In the graph below I have plotted the Mean and Standard Deviation of the exact Goldbach Prime Pairs per partition against the Prime Number Theorem Deduced average GPP estimates. We can see that the Mean of the exact computed GPPs and the PMT deduced GPPs are virtually the

same. Also using Excel regression for both the Mean and the Standard Deviation of the Goldbach Prime Pairs I got R^2 incredibly close to 1, thus showing very precise patterns.

Figure 1:

Here it is useful to note the Equation for the regression graph of the Mean of the exact Goldbach Prime Pairs suggested by Excel: (*Equation 1*)

$$y = 0.0905x^{0.8017} \quad (1)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9998 \quad (2)$$

I then decided to compare above regression equation with $\frac{N}{\ln N}$ using the constant of proportionality, 0.19, that Mikki and I discovered in our February 2023 paper (see "*Why the Goldbach conjecture is likely true*", *Ismael Afaf and Mikhael Afaf, 18th Feb 2023*). Since the constant of proportionality was for the number of 2-primes, i need half trhe number for pairs of primres. Therefore, I have graphed with a proportion of 0.095. The equation used in the graph was therefore : $y = \frac{0.95N}{\ln N}$

I didn't have time to graph the GPP approximation $Li(X) \approx \frac{N}{\ln N} + \frac{N}{\ln N^2} + \frac{2N}{\ln N^3}$ (see "*How the Prime Number Theorem likely implies not just the simple Goldbach Conjecture but a much stronger version*", *Ismael Afaf, 22nd Jun 2023*) although it would have been likely an even better fit as suggested in my previous paper, but for now the simpler approximation suffices in making the comparison.

Figure 2:

3 The Relationship between Average Goldbach Prime Pairs and the Standard Deviation

Now note the Excel suggested regression equation for the Standard Deviation of Goldbach Prime Pairs is:

$$y = 0.0352x^{8018} \quad (3)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9986 \quad (4)$$

This very high R^2 with the same functional form as for the Mean suggests a very close relationship between the Mean and Standard Deviation. I therefore graphed the ratio of the Mean to the Standard Deviation of GPPs below, finding the ratio fluctuates in a tight band around 2.567

Figure 3:

I do not have a precise explanation or ability to derive the graph from the Prime Number Theorem at this point, but the relation between the Mean and Standard Deviation is not entirely unintuitive.

Imagine for example the pair (47,53) adding up to 100. As we now look at the next even number, 102, the number of primes hardly changes

- the change being either 0 or 1 depending on whether 101 is non-prime or prime. But now looking at 53, it pairs up with 49 instead to make 102. So the prime pair (47, 53) for 100 including 53 as prime, is now no longer a prime pair including 53, for the number 102. In this way some prime numbers drop out from being part of prime pairs as even numbers increase, while others drop in. As an example consider (5, 95) as a non GPP pair for the number 100. As we move to the even number 102, the prime number 5 now pairs with 97 to make 102, so the prime 5 is now part of a GPP prime pair. As we keep increasing even numbers, prime numbers keep dropping in and out of GPPs, giving the oscillation we observe. But it is not surprising that resulting standard deviation of GPPs is very closely linked to the average number of GPPs in a partition, which is what we observe.

Maybe I can deduce this behaviour from the Prime Number Theorem as well, just like the Mean number of GPPs I deduced in my previous paper, but this is not clear as the PMT seems to deal only with an approximate average.

4 References

1. *"Why the Goldbach conjecture is likely true", Ismael Afaf and Mikhael Afaf, 18th Feb 2023*
2. *"How the Prime Number Theorem likely implies not just the simple Goldbach Conjecture but a much stronger version", Ismael Afaf, 22nd Jun 2023*